

BDAIM-2025

PROCEEDINGS

of the International Scientific and Practical Conference

Big Data and Artificial Intelligence in Modeling
International Socio-Economic Processes

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

May 27, 2025

University of World Economy and Diplomacy
Moscow State Institute of International Relations
National University of Uzbekistan

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Big Data & AI for Global Socio-
Economic Modeling

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in Modeling

International Socio-Economic Processes

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(Conference Proceedings)

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International Scientific and Practical Conference – BDAIM-2025

Big Data and Artificial Intelligence in Modeling International Socio-Economic Processes

The **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**, in collaboration with **MGIMO University** and the **National University of Uzbekistan (NUUz)**, hosted the international scientific and practical conference **BDAIM-2025** on **May 27, 2025** in **Tashkent, Uzbekistan**.

The main **goal** of the conference was to unite researchers, policy makers, experts, and educators to explore cutting-edge applications of **big data** and **artificial intelligence (AI)** in modeling **international socio-economic processes**. Particular emphasis was placed on interdisciplinary approaches and digital transformation in economics, governance, and education.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **Theoretical Foundations:** big data processing, machine learning algorithms, interpretability.
- **Socio-Economic Modeling:** global trade, finance, migration, and digital economies.
- **Global Challenges:** AI for climate change, pandemics, geopolitical risk management.
- **International Relations:** digital diplomacy, media analytics, conflict forecasting.
- **Ethics and Regulation:** AI governance, data protection, algorithmic responsibility.
- **Mathematical Models:** econometrics, game theory, uncertainty and risk analysis.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Sun'iy intellekt rivojlanishi sharoitida IBM korporatsiyasida o'zgarishlarni boshqarish tendensiyalari

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15510728>

XXI asrda transmilliy korporatsiyalarni boshqarish strategiyalari - raqamlashtirish, ilmiy-texnologik inqilob va ijtimoiy jarayonlar transformatsiyasi kabi zamonaviy omillar ta'sirida sezilarli o'zgarishlarni boshdan kechirmoqda. Ushbu o'zgarishlar tashkilotlardan o'zgarishlarni boshqarishga kompleks yondashuvni, shu jumladan, o'zgarishlarni tushunish, ularni to'g'ri yo'naltirish va samarali boshqarishni talab qiladi. So'nggi 5 yil ichida sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining jadal sur'atlarda rivojlanishi biznes subyektlarini boshqarishda - zamonaviy menejmentning dastlabki tasavvurlarni o'zgartirmoqda va an'anaviy boshqaruv amaliyotini qayta ko'rib chiqishni talab qiladi.

O'zgarishlarni boshqarish kontseptsiyasining asosida yangi g'oyalarni qo'llash orqali tizimning barqarorligini ta'minlovchi kuchlarni o'zgartirishga bo'lgan xohishni amalga oshirilishi yotadi. U innovatsion faoliyat bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lib, o'zgarishlarni samarali jalb qilish uchun qo'llanilishi mumkin bo'lgan g'oyalar, strategiyalar va ko'nikmalar to'plami sifatida e'tirof etiladi. Bu kompleks jarayon bo'lib, o'zgarishni amalga oshirish bilan birga o'zgarishlarga jalb qilingan insonlar va tizimlarni tayyorlash, qo'llab-quvvatlash va moslashishiga yordam berishni nazarda tutadi.

O'zgarishlarni boshqarishga etakchi korporatsiyalardan biri International Business Machines (IBM) korporatsiyasi hisoblanadi; u xalqaro bozorda 113 yillik faoliyati davomida tashqi muhitdagi imkoniyat va xavflardan unumli foydalanishga va ularni samarali boshqarishga muvaffaq bo'lgan. Bugungi kunda IBM korporatsiyasi 175 dan ortiq mamlakatda faoliyat yuritadi, 108 ta sho'ba korxonalariga, 6 ta mintaqada joylashgan 19 ta ilmiy-tadqiqot laboratoriyalariga ega; 293 mingdan ortiq xodimni ish bilan ta'minlaydi. IBM global bulutli texnologiyalar bozorining 2% va server yechimlari segmentining 3,2% ulushiga ega. 2024-yil yakunlari bo'yicha korporatsiya \$62,7 mlrd daromad va \$206 mlrd bozor kapitallashuviga erishib, dunyoning eng yirik dasturiy ta'minot yetkazib beruvchilari qatoridan o'rin oldi [6]. IBM korporatsiyasining 18 mahsuloti 13 toifada G2 Best Software Awards 2025 mukofotini qo'lga kiritdi. Xususan, IBM watsonx Assistant va watsonx.ai - sun'iy intellekt sohasidagi eng yaxshi yechimlar deb topildi [5]; TrustRadius Buyer's Choice Awards 2025 doirasida IBM mijozlarning yuqori darajadagi qoniqishini ta'minlagani uchun IBM Apptio va IBM Cloudability yechimlari bilan e'tirof etildi, IBM SPSS Statistics esa narx va sifat nisbatining a'lo darajadali, funktsionalligi hamda mijozlarga ko'rsatilgan yordami uchun mukofotga sazovor bo'ldi [7]. Shuni ta'kidlash joizki, bugungi kunda IBM'ning sun'iy intellekt sohasidagi biznes portfeli 6 milliard dollar qiymatga ega [8].

IBM korporatsiyasi faoliyati asosan 4 ta segmentda asoslanadi, bular dasturiy ta'minot, konsalting, infratuzilmalar va moliya segmentlaridir. 2023-yil holatiga ko'ra IBMga eng yuqori daromad keltirgan segment bu dasturiy ta'minot bo'lib, umumiy hisobda

korporatsiyasiga tahminan \$26 mlrd daromad keltirgan. Konsalting xizmatlaridan kelgan daromad tahminan \$20 mlrdni tashkil etdi. Infratuzilmalar segmentidan kelgan daromad \$14.593 mlrd bo'ldi. Moliyaviy xizmatlar ko'rsatish orqali esa korporatsiya \$741 mln teng daromadga erishdi [4].

Rasm 1. IBM korporatsiyasining so'nggi 10 yillik umumiy daromadi va uning o'sish dinamikasi

Manba: IBM ning 2015-2024 yillik moliyaviy hisobotlari asosida mualliflar tomonidan tuzilgan;
[https://www.ibm.com/downloads/IBM Annual Reports/us-en/2017-2024](https://www.ibm.com/downloads/IBM%20Annual%20Reports/us-en/2017-2024)

Korporatsiyaning global bozorda faoliyati tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki, 2024-yil so'nggi moliyaviy choragida umumiy daromadning \$5,8 mlrd Yevropa, Yaqin Sharq va Afrikaga to'g'ri kelib, 33,04% ni tashkil etgan. Yil davomida Osiyo-Tinch Okeani mintaqasi \$3,2 mlrd daromad keltirgan va bu umumiy daromadning 18,23% ni tashkil etgan. Daromadning katta qismi Amerika mintaqasiga to'g'ri keladi va bu umumiy daromadning tahminan 47% tashkil qilgan.

Rasm 2. IBM ning 2024-yilda umumiy daromadning mintaqalar bo'yicha taqsimlanishi

Manba: IBM ning 2015-2024 yillik moliyaviy hisobotlari asosida mualliflar tomonidan tuzilgan;
[https://www.ibm.com/downloads/IBM Annual Reports/us-en/2017-2024](https://www.ibm.com/downloads/IBM%20Annual%20Reports/us-en/2017-2024) Manba: Yahoo Finance tomonidan

berilgan ma'lumotlar asosida mualliflar tomonidan tuzilgan; IBM (IBM) International Revenue Performance Explored

Shuni ta'kidlash joizki, 2024-yilda dunyodagi eng yirik o'nta sun'iy intellekt ishlab chiqaruvchilarining umumiy bozor kapitallashuvi \$16 trlnni tashkil etgan. Xususan, IBM ham o'zining sun'iy intellekt sohasidagi muvaffaqiyatli innovatsion ishlanmalari yordamida ushbu o'nlik ichida 8-o'rinni egallagan.

Rasm 3. IBM korporatsiyasining so'nggi 10 yillik umumiy daromadi va uning o'sish dinamikasiBozor kapitalizatsiya bo'yicha dunyodagi eng yirik sun'iy intellekt ishlab chiqaruvchilarning TOP-10 taligi

Manba: Companies Market Camp ma'lumotlari asosida mualliflar tomonidan tuzilgan
<https://companiesmarketcap.com/artificial-intelligence/largest-ai-companies-by-marketcap>

IBM kuchli raqobat sharoitida, o'z raqobatchilaridan ortda qolmaslik va doimiy iqtisodiy o'sishga erishish uchun tadqiqot va rivojlanishga juda katta mablag' ajratuvchi korporatsiya sifatida tan olinadi. Hozirda IBM sun'iy intellekt, bulutli texnologiyalar va kvant hisoblash texnologiyalari kabi ilg'or sohalarga faol sarmoya kiritmoqda. IBM uning ushbu sohalardagi innovatsiyalari 2024-yilda 7 mlrd AQSH dollaridan ortiq tadqiqot va rivojlanish (R&D) xarajatlari bilan qoplangan. 2014-2019 yillar oraliq'ida IBM ning R&D ga sarflagan xarajatlari sof foydaga sezirarli ta'sir qilganini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Ammo, sof foydaning 2017-yildan boshlab \$5.75 mlrdga pasayishi IBM ni R&D ga xarajatlarni oshirishga majburlagan. Pandemiya davridan boshlab IBM R&D faoliyatini keskin kengaytirgan va bu orqali zamonaviy texnologiyalarga asoslangan mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishni maqsad qilgan. Ushbu yondashuv kompaniya tomonidan uzoq muddatli strategik qaror sifatida qabul qilinib, kelajakda innovatsiyalardan barqaror daromad olishni ko'zlaydi.

Rasm 4. IBM korporatsiyasi R&D xarajatlari va sof foyda ko'rsatkichlarining 2014–2024 yillardagi dinamikasi

Manba: IBM ning 2015-2024 yillik moliyaviy hisobotlari asosida mualliflar tomonidan tuzilgan;
[https://www.ibm.com/downloads/IBM Annual Reports/us-en/2017-2024](https://www.ibm.com/downloads/IBM%20Annual%20Reports/us-en/2017-2024)

IBM sun'iy intellektning keskin rivojlanishiga faqatgina hissa qo'shayotgan emas, balki moslashayotgan korporatsiya hamdir. Sun'iy intellekt sohasida yetakchilik qilish uchun kompaniya o'zining ichki boshqaruv tizimini yangilashga, yangi biznes modellarini yaratishga va ijtimoiy mas'uliyatli yondashuvlarni amaliyotga tatbiq qilishga muhim e'tibor qaratmoqda. Tahlillar kompaniya sun'iy intellekt va avtomatlashtirish texnologiyalarini insonlarning kundalik faoliyati, xizmat ko'rsatish jarayonlari va mijozlarga xizmat ko'rsatish tizimlarida faol qo'llash orqali o'zgaruvchan muhitga moslashish zaruratini chuqur anglaganini ko'rsatdi. Xususan, IBM Watson chatbotlarini qo'llovchi tibbiyot muassasalari sun'iy intellektidan foydalanib, klinik ma'lumotlarni boshqaradi, natijada bemorlarning xarajatlarni va kutish vaqtlarini kamaytiradi [2]. Moliya sohasida IBM sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalari orqali banklar va sug'urta kompaniyalari mijozlariga xizmat ko'rsatishni takomillashtirmoqda. IBM Watsonx Assistant yordamida sug'urta kompaniyalari mijozlarga polis tanlash, da'volarni topshirish va to'lovlarni amalga oshirishda yordam beradigan sun'iy intellekt chatbotlarini yaratish ustida ish olib bormoqdalar. IBMning o'zgarishlarni boshqarish strategiyasi faqatgina texnologik yangilanishlar bilan cheklanmaydi, balki tashkilotning tashkiliy tuzilmasi, inson resurslari siyosati va global bozordagi o'zgaruvchan sharoitlarga moslashish kabi keng qamrovli masalalarni ham o'z ichiga oladi.

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